

Surgical Evaluation in a Patient With a Cecal Injury During Laparoscopic Appendectomy

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Abstract: Background: The large intestine is divided into several parts, with the first being a cecum. In such cases, laparoscopic cecectomy is a feasible treatment option for some patients.

Aim: The objective of this study is to evaluate the surgical outcomes of patients with cecal injury who underwent laparoscopic surgery in comparison with patients without cecal injury.

Patients and methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted on 96 patients with cecum who had undergone laparoscopic appendectomy. The participants were divided into two groups, comprising male and female subjects, respectively. The initial group comprised 48 patients with a cecum who had undergone laparoscopic appendectomy. The second group comprised 48 patients who had undergone appendectomy but did not have a cecum. All surgical, demographic, and postoperative outcomes were recorded, including complications, time to first bowel movement, and postoperative quality of life, for patients in both groups.

Results: The findings presented herein encompass the surgical data of patients. In a cohort of patients without cecal injury, the mean surgical time was 56.28 ± 8.04 minutes, with intraoperative bleeding observed in six cases. The mean postoperative pain score was 3.27 ± 1.03 , with a mean hospital stay of 5.17 ± 1.72 days. The mean time to first bowel movement was 1.35 ± 0.45 days, and the mortality rate was 2%. The mortality rate was 4.17%, and the incidence of postoperative complications was 21%. The mean surgical time was 59.83 ± 10.12 minutes, with intraoperative bleeding occurring in 8 cases. The mean postoperative pain score was 3.88 ± 0.75 , with a mean hospital stay of 7.26 ± 3.01 days. The mean time to first bowel movement was 2.62 ± 0.94 days.

Conclusion: For patients with cecal, laparoscopic appendectomy (LA) may have a big impact, especially on recovery and complications.

Keywords: Cecal injury; Laparoscopic Approach; appendix; Complications; Recovery; and Quality of Life.

Introduction

Because the cecum is the first segment of the large intestine, patients with cecal involvement of appendicitis provide a special challenge to surgeons [1,2]. When the inflammation of the appendix has spread into the cecum, surgery, called an appendectomy, is frequently the best line of therapy. [3,4,5]

Infection, bleeding, and even problems with bowel motions are possible post-operative risks. For patients who have experienced their cecum affected by appendicitis, post-operative treatment must

include monitoring for infection symptoms, making sure wounds are properly cared for, and adhering to a prescribed diet. [6,7,8,9,10]

Postoperative Pain Management: Following LA, patients usually have fewer problems and need less analgesics [11,12]. Despite the benefits of laparoscopic procedures, careful surgical strategy and execution are required because to the possibility of major complications such as cecal volvulus and unintentional damage [13,14]. In surgical practice, striking a balance between the advantages of minimally invasive procedures with the dangers of cecal damage is still crucial. [15]

Methodology

A cross-sectional study was conducted on 96 patients who were undergoing appendectomy surgery. All data, indicators, and patient outcomes were recorded. The data pertaining to the participants in this study were collected from different hospitals in Iraq over the course of a period spanning from February 2023 to January 2024. The data pertaining to the participating patients, whose ages ranged between 20 and 50 years, were organized according to body mass index (BMI) categories, including underweight, normal weight, overweight, and obesity. The demographic data included age, gender, BMI, smoking status, nutritional status, and educational and economic status.

With regard to the surgical outcomes, all patients who underwent appendectomy were diagnosed. The study groups were divided into two categories: one comprising patients with cecal involvement who underwent appendectomy (n = 48) and the other comprising patients without cecal involvement who underwent appendectomy (n = 48). The diagnostic parameters of the patients were recorded, including the causes and degree of appendicitis, using the Alvarado score, which ranges from 0 to 10, with 0 indicating no appendicitis and 10 indicating severe appendicitis. Additionally, indicators of cecal disease, appendicitis, other comorbidities, and other data were documented. Patients were sampled and examined for white blood cells, blood pressure, and cholesterol and underwent imaging tests, including ultrasound, computed tomography, and magnetic resonance imaging.

For the purposes of this study, data was recorded pertaining to the surgical outcomes of laparoscopic appendectomy procedures. These included operative time, blood loss, and the percentage of patients who experienced bleeding during surgery. Additionally, data was collected on the rate of patients experiencing pain, the length of hospital stay, the incidence of complications, the time to first bowel movement, the use of oral and intravenous analgesics in patients after surgery, and the mortality rate. The SF-36 assessment questionnaire was employed to evaluate the quality of life of both male and female patients. This entailed the assessment of the general health of patients participating in the study on a scale of 0 to 100, with 0 representing low scores (indicating poor health-related quality of life) and 100 representing high scores (indicating optimal health-related quality of life).

Results TABLE 1. DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PATIENTS.

Variables	No. of patients [N = 96]	Percentage, %
Age, years		
20 – 30	25	26.6%
31 – 40	50	53.19%
41 – 50	19	20.21%
Sex		
Males	66	70.21%
Females	28	29.79%
BMI, Kg/m ²		
Underweight	4	4.26%
Normal weight	8	8.51%
Overweight	34	36.17%
Obesity	48	51.06%
Smoking status		
Yes	57	60.64%

No	37	39.36%
Malnutrition		
Yes	77	81.91%
No	17	18.09%
Education level		
Illiterate	7	7.45%
Primary	17	18.09%
Secondary	20	21.28%
Undergraduate	14	14.89%
Postgraduate	36	38.30%
Income status, \$		
< 600	40	42.55%
600 – 900	34	36.17%
> 900	20	21.28%

TABLE 2. ENROLLING INDICATORS AND EXAMINATION DATA OF PARTICIPANTS IN THIS STUDY.

Variables	Patients without cecal injury		Patients with cecal injury	
	[N = 48]	%	[N = 48]	%
Causes				
Virus	5	10.42%	8	16.67%
Bacteria	43	89.58%	40	83.33%
Alvarado score				
Low, 0 – 4	3	6.25%	2	4.17%
Intermediate, 5 – 6	8	16.67%	6	12.5%
High, 7 – 10	37	77.08%	40	83.33%
Indicators of appendix				
Pain	15	31.25%	-	-
Loss of appetite	5	10.42%	-	-
Nausea	7	14.58%	-	-
Vomiting	4	8.33%	-	-
Abdominal swelling	10	20.83%	-	-
Fever	7	7.45%	-	-
Indicators of cecal injury				
Severe abdominal pain	-	-	20	41.67%
Nausea	-	-	3	6.25%
Vomiting	-	-	4	8.33%
Fever	-	-	2	4.17%
Bloating	-	-	6	12.50%
Inability to pass gas or stool	-	-	8	8.51%
Rectal bleeding	-	-	3	3.19%
Rapid heartbeat	-	-	2	2.13%
Low blood pressure	-	-	20	41.67%
No. of comorbidities				
Hypertension	14	29.17%	24	50.0%
Asthma	11	22.92%	10	20.83%
Anemia	4	8.33%	2	4.17%
Diabetes	15	31.25%	9	18.75%
Others	4	8.33%	3	6.25%
Leukocyte count				
<10,000	8	16.67%	10	20.83%

10,000–15,000	36	75.0%	30	62.50%
>15,000	4	8.33%	8	16.67%
Blood pressure				
Diastolic	73.85 ± 26.27		76.94 ± 28.44	
Systolic	120.35 ± 39.56		124.49 ± 35.51	
Cholesterol				
Normal	9	18.75%	5	10.42%
Moderate	18	37.50%	17	35.42%
Severe	21	43.75%	26	54.17%
Imaging tests				
Ultrasound	16	33.33%	16	33.33%
CT scans	20	41.67%	19	39.58%
MRI	12	25.0%	13	27.08%
Procedure use				
laparoscopic	c	100%	48	100%

TABLE 3. SURGICAL DATA OF PARTICIPANTS.

Variables	Patients without cecal injury		Patients with cecal injury	
	[N = 48]	%	[N = 48]	%
Surgical time, min	56.28 ± 8.04		59.83 ± 10.12	
Intraoperative Bleeding, n (%)				
Yes	6	12.5%	8	16.67%
No	42	87.5%	40	83.33%
Postoperative pain	3.27 ± 1.03		3.88 ± 0.75	
Hospital stays, days	5.17 ± 1.72		7.26 ± 3.01	
Postoperative examine				
Time to first bowel movement (days)	1.35 ± 0.45		2.62 ± 0.94	
Oral analgesics (days)	3.19 ± 0.50		3.78 ± 0.65	
Parenteral analgesics (days)	1.05 ± 0.17		1.60 ± 0.53	
Mortality rate, %				
Yes	1	2.08%	2	4.17%
No	47	97.92%	46	95.83%

FIGURE 1: POST – OPERATIVE COMPLICATIONS OF BOTH GROUPS: (A) PATIENTS WITHOUT CECAL INJURY, (B) PATIENTS WITH CECAL INJURY.

TABLE 4. ASSESSMENT OF GENERAL HEALTH QUALITY OF LIFE IN-OPERATIVE DATA OBSERVED IN OUR STUDY.

Items	SF – 36 Questionnaire	
	Patients without cecal injury	Patients with cecal injury
Physical functioning	78.11 ± 4.26	67.21 ± 8.15
Psychological Functioning	83.91 ± 3.10	81.17 ± 6.87
Emotional and social functioning	73.29 ± 5.36	78.66 ± 4.75
Daily activity	77.56 ± 3.76	84.20 ± 6.31

Discussion

A total of 94 patients who underwent to laparoscopic appendectomy. The first group was 48 patients without cecal injury and 48 patients with cecal injury.

Some studies [16,17,18] found patients enduring a laparoscopic appendectomy involving a cecum may benefit from less invasive surgery, which might result in less post-operative discomfort, shorter hospital stays, and, therefore, a quicker recovery. However, depending on their unique anatomy, people lacking a cecum can require alternative surgical techniques and other concerns throughout the surgery. The current findings found postoperative pain was 5.17 ± 1.72 , hospital stays were 5.17 ± 1.72 , intraoperative bleeding had 6 cases, time to first bowel movement was 1.35 ± 0.45 days, and only one death case in the first group, while 3.88 ± 0.75 , hospital stays were 7.26 ± 3.01 , time to first bowel movement was 2.62 ± 0.94 days, and only two death cases were in the second group.

Insights into the surgical results and possible variations in recovery may be gained by comparing the frequency of postoperative complications between the two groups, including surgical area infection, intra-abdominal abscess development, and post-operative ileus. In light of the minimally invasive nature of laparoscopic appendectomy, individuals with a cecum may experience fewer complications, while those without one may encounter particular difficulties in the post-operative phase [19,20]. In our outcomes, we found the rate of complication was 17% in the first group and 21% in the second group, where the significant factor were intra-abdominal abscess, which occurred in both groups.

Other studies [21,22,23] have shown that it is also possible to compare long-term results between the two groups, including the prevalence of chronic abdominal discomfort, bowel function, and quality of life. Laparoscopic appendectomy patients with a cecum may have better long-term results than those without one, possibly as a result of the advantages in minimally invasive surgery for recuperation and general health. In the questionnaire of quality-life assessment, we found that psychological Functioning was 83.91 ± 3.10 and physical functioning was 78.11 ± 4.26 in the first group, while psychological Functioning was 81.17 ± 6.87 and physical functioning was 67.21 ± 8.15 in the second group.

Furthermore, understanding the comprehensive care given to those in both groups can be facilitated by talking about the variations in follow-up treatment, such as the necessity of imaging tests, post-operative visits, and food advice. Recovery can be accelerated, and any problems can be avoided by customizing follow-up therapy for patients who have or do not have a cecum. [24]

In our findings, we noticed that clinical practice guidelines can be developed and determined by the comparison of the two groups. Enhancing surgical results and patient satisfaction can be achieved by determining optimal procedures for patients having laparoscopic appendectomy who have a cecum and those who do not.

Conclusion

The current findings shown shorter hospital stays, a speedier return to regular activities, and less operating time were among the intra- and post-operative benefits of laparoscopic appendectomy. Additionally, our findings indicate a reduction in complications among patients with cecum and an improvement in their quality of life.

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